

DYNAMIC DEFORMATION AND MICROSTRUCTURAL RESPONSE OF IN SITU TiB_w/Ti6Al4V COMPOSITES

J. Sun^a, H. Wang^a, L.J. Huang^b, L.Geng^b, F.X. Qin^a, H.X. Peng^{a*}

^a Institute for Composites Science Innovation (InCSI), School of Materials Science and Engineering, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou 310027, PR China

^b School of Materials Science and Engineering, Harbin Institute of Technology, P.O. Box 433, Harbin 150001, PR China

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic deformation behavior of a 3.5% TiB_w/Ti6Al4V titanium matrix composite with quasi-continuous network microstructure^[1] were investigated by compressive split Hopkinson pressure bar(SHPB). The dynamic compression tests were conducted at 1000s⁻¹ to 3500s⁻¹ and the microstructural evolution as well as subsequent deformation mechanisms of this quasi-continuous network TiB_w/Ti6Al4V was investigated by optical microscope, scanning electron microscope, electron backscatter diffraction and transmission electron microscopy. A simple analytical model that incorporates evolving damage within the composite was proposed, and shown that the analytical predictions are consistent with the experimental observations over a wide range of strain rates.

True stress-strain curves got from SHPB experiments are shown in Fig.1. Dynamic responses of the composite show a rate-sensitivity. Slight strain hardening is observed at 1000s⁻¹, 1500s⁻¹ and 2000s⁻¹ with the tendency of decreasing with increasing strain rates, while it disappears when the strain rate getting 2700s⁻¹. Reasons for this phenomenon may be the stronger effect of adiabatic thermal softening with increasing strain rates which would be such as to reduce the apparent strain hardening in high strain rates experiments. The yield limits were measured using the method in Literature^[2], which takes the intersection of lines projected from the initial elastic modulus and the slope of the extended plastic deformation plateau as yield limit. Yield limit measured at different strain rates appears a sensitivity to strain rates shown in Fig.2, indicating higher strain rates improve the effect of strain hardening.

Fig.1 True stress-strain curves at different strain rates

Fig.2 Dynamic yield limits for TiBw/Ti6Al4V composites deformed at different strain rates

Initial point ε_i and termination point ε_t of plastic flow were measured at the point in stress-strain curves where the data meet the equation (1), and impact absorbing energy of plastic deformation E and average flow stress $\bar{\sigma}_f$ were calculated according to the equation (2). These data are shown in Table.1 and fitted in Fig.3a) and Fig.3b). The polynomials fitting curves in Fig.3a) and Fig.3b) indicate there are some common factors behind them and we are still exploring mechanism of the phenomenon by more compressive SHPB experiments.

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\varepsilon} \right)'_{\varepsilon} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Fig.3 a) E-strain rate curve and Fig.3b) average flow stress-strain rate at different strain rate

$$E = \int_{\varepsilon_i}^{\varepsilon_t} \sigma d\varepsilon$$

$$\overline{\sigma}_f = \frac{E}{\varepsilon_t - \varepsilon_i} \quad (2)$$

strain rates/s ⁻¹	ε_i	ε_t	$E / MJ \cdot m^{-3}$	$\overline{\sigma}_f / MPa$
1000	0.0602	0.0857	36.22	1420.39
1500	0.0651	0.1194	78.56	1446.78
2000	0.0822	0.145	91.34	1454.46
2700	0.1061	0.1647	85.86	1465.19
3000	0.1131	0.1831	103.1	1472.86
3500	0.1238	0.192	100.3	1470.67

Table.1 Dynamic parameters at different strain rates

Then we did simulations to the data of plastic flow of specimens at different strain rates. The point at yield stress was set to be the initiation of plastic flow and the point at 90 percent of the maximum flow stress was taken as the termination of plastic flow. According to Johnson-Cook model, plastic flow curves are related to strain, strain rate and temperature as the equation (3).

$$\sigma = \left[A + B \cdot (\varepsilon^p)^n \right] \cdot \left[1 + C \cdot \ln \dot{\varepsilon}^* \right] \cdot \left[1 - (T^*)^m \right] \quad (3)$$

where A,B,C are constants decided by materials, n is strain hardening coefficient, m is thermal coefficient, $\dot{\varepsilon}^*$, T^* are relative strain rate and relative temperature respectively.

According to our experiments data, we modified the equation (3) slightly to the equation

(4).

$$\sigma = \left[A + B \cdot (\varepsilon^p)^n \right] \cdot \left[1 + C \cdot \ln \dot{\varepsilon}^* \right] \cdot \left[1 - D \cdot (T^*)^m \right] \quad (4)$$

Where D is also a constant decided by the material.

We set the standard strain rate as 1 s⁻¹ and standard temperature as 273K, and got the coefficients as Table 2.

Table 2. Values of coefficients calculated from experiments data

coefficient	value	coefficient	value
A	1253	D	2.6158
B	3897	n	0.8572
C	0.0147	m	0.6784

Using these values, the experimental plastic stress-strain curves and simulative plastic stress-strain curves are shown as Fig.4(a)-(d).

(a) 1000s⁻¹

(b) 1500s⁻¹

(c) 2000s⁻¹

(d) 3000s⁻¹

Fig.4 Comparison between the experimental and the simulative plastic stress-strain curves

Optical micrographs of post-loading specimens show apparent adiabatic shear bands

(ASB) in the composite (Fig.4), which are usually seen as symbol of materials failure, when getting strain rates of 2700s^{-1} . There are also cracks induced by ASB we found in some situations which corresponding to others' research results, shown in Fig.5a). When suffering from SHPB experiments, the network microstructure of reinforcement became flat with the orientation at an angle of about 45° with respect to the loading direction and left evidences for plastic flow, shown in Fig.5b).

Fig.4. adiabatic shear bands (ASB) observed in specimen at strain rate of 2700s^{-1}

Fig.5. a) Cracks induced by ASB in specimen at strain rate of 2700s^{-1} and Fig.5. b) the change of network microstructure of specimen after SHPB

SEM micrographs show there are typical symbols of flowing in ASB shown as Fig.6a) and Fig.6b). Evidence shows the reinforcement in the composite hinders the flow in ASB shown as Fig.7.

Fig.6a) ASB in specimen at strain rate at $2700s^{-1}$ Fig.6b) ASB in specimen at strain rate at $3000s^{-1}$

Fig.7 Reinforcement hinders flow in ASB

TEM micrographs and selected area electron diffraction(SAED) indicate fine grains formed in ASB.

Fig.8a) TEM micrograph of ASB at $3000s^{-1}$

Fig.8b)SAED in ASB at $3000s^{-1}$

Titanium matrix composites show enormous potential in many fields like aviation, armoured cars where they suffer from dynamic impacts, so it is meaningful to research on dynamic responses of this new type of titanium matrix composite and explore the mechanism

behind them to offer guidance to design and preparation of new whisker-reinforced titanium matrix composites in the future.

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